

Using the densimeter

Trinn	Aksjon	Bilder	Kommentar
<p>Document title: Using the densimeter</p> <p>Laboratory location: University of Stavanger (UiS)</p> <p>Scope: This procedure describes the laboratory method used to measure fluid density with the densimeter for the model fluids used in this thesis. It includes instrument preparation, verification with distilled water, sample injection, recording of density values, and cleaning after use.</p>			
<p>Preparation before testing with the densimeter</p>			
1.	Find a pipette. It is located on the densimeter.		
2.	Open the cap of the distilled water and use a pipette to draw water into it. Remember to close the cap again when you are finished.		
3.	Check whether there are any air bubbles inside the pipette. In the picture, you can see a small bubble. Expel a little water and tap the pipette gently until the bubble bursts, then dispense the water as shown in the picture so that no air bubbles remain. See the pictures.		

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			<p>It should appear as shown before it is injected into the densimeter.</p>
4.	Pull out the tube.		
5.	Insert the pipette containing distilled water into the opening from which the tube was removed, and carefully inject the water.		<p>It is important to insert the pipette fully into the opening and not pull it out after the injection. Leave the pipette in place.</p>

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6.	Press Start, as shown in the figure. Wait until the instrument is ready; it will reach 15 °C		
7.	The densimeter display should show a series of lines, as illustrated in the figure. Confirm that the density of water is approximately 1.000 g/cm ³ at standard laboratory conditions.		If this value is not obtained, repeat the procedure until a satisfactory result is achieved.
<p>Inject the sample into the densimeter.</p>			
1.	Use a new pipette before injecting the sample into the densimeter.		The figure shows a pipette containing a xanthan–water sample injected into the densimeter.

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2.	A density value will be displayed. Record it on a sheet of paper or take a photograph. Ensure that both the sample identification and the measured density are documented.		
Reset the densimeter to conclude the test			
1.	Use distilled water and inject it as shown in the figures until lines appear on the display.		
2.	Inject acetone, as shown in the figures, until lines appear on the display.		

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3.	Reinsert the tube.		
4.	Press “Pump” and wait approximately 30–60 seconds. You will hear a sound from the instrument as it pumps air.		
5.	Press “Pump” again to stop the pumping. You will hear that the sound has stopped.		
6.	Discard the pipette, check for any spills, and clean up your workspace. Close the fume hood.		

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